

24 July 2024

Press release

The CST4ALL project hosted the online “Industry Workshop on the hybridisation of Concentrated Solar Thermal Technologies (CST) with biomass” on 7 May 2024. The workshop aimed to assess the industrial potential of concepts integrating biomass technologies with parts of the CST value chain. Organised by ESTELA in collaboration with all CST4ALL partners and supported by the European Technology and Innovation Platform Bioenergy (ETIP Bioenergy), the event brought together over 90 stakeholders from the energy sector across 17 countries within and outside Europe.

The workshop attracted a diverse range of stakeholders, including representatives from the European Commission, national authorities, industry, associations, engineering and consultancy firms, research institutions and universities.

Dr. Konstantinos Genikomsakis of ESTELA opened the workshop by introducing the CST4ALL project, outlining the workshop objectives and agenda, and inviting the attendees to participate in the on-going public opinion survey on Green Deal challenges & social sciences and humanities and gender aspects in the framework of the project.

Elisabeth Schellmann from the European Commission followed with a welcome message setting the EU policy scene. More specifically, Elisabeth Schellmann emphasized the importance of a competitive clean energy manufacturing sector in Europe, highlighted CST's potential in contributing to EU's clean energy goals and encouraged collaboration between policymakers, researchers and industry to develop innovative clean energy solutions that combine CST with other renewable energy technologies.

The workshop featured keynote presentations by experts from the CST and biomass sectors, namely Yuvaraj Sathiyadev Pandian from Solarlite CSP Technology GmbH, Morten Tony Hansen from Ea Energy Analyses/IEA Bioenergy Task 32 Biomass Combustion and Poul Vestergaard Jensen from Brønderslev Forsyning A/S. The keynote speakers explored the possibilities and challenges of CST-biomass integration and presented successful application examples, including the case study of the CST-biomass hybrid plant for district heating in Brønderslev, Denmark.

A live poll engaged the audience by asking them to rank key factors for successful deployment of hybrid CST-biomass plants in Europe. Bankability of projects emerged as the top concern, followed by market potential and project pipeline to stimulate manufacturing.

A roundtable discussion, moderated by Dr. Derek Baker of ODTÜ-GÜNAM Center for Solar Energy Research and Applications, featured industry, research and funding agency experts who addressed aspects related to industrial maturity and applications, project financing and risk mitigation, regional

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integration, skills and workforce, market potential, R&I contributions and priorities, as well as synergies and collaboration opportunities.

Dr. Peter Heller, coordinator of the CST4ALL project, concluded the workshop by summarising the main takeaways from each session. The event highlighted the significant potential of hybrid CST-biomass technologies for clean, reliable, and secure energy generation. While challenges remain, particularly regarding project financing and integration complexity, collaboration between stakeholders across industry, research, and policy can significantly advance the deployment of this promising technology.

This CST4ALL project event is organised with the support of the European Technology and Innovation Platform Bioenergy (ETIP Bioenergy).

CST4ALL Coordinator

**Deutsches Zentrum
für Luft- und Raumfahrt e.V.**
in der Helmholtz-Gemeinschaft

DLR: Deutsches Zentrum fuer Luft - Und Raumfahrt EV (DE)

CST4ALL Partners

CIEMAT: Centro de Investigaciones Energeticas, Medioambientales y Tecnologicas (ES)

ENEA: Agenzia nazionale per le nuove tecnologie, l'energia e lo sviluppo economico sostenibile (IT)

ESTELA: European Solar Thermal Electricity Association (BE)

GUNAM: Center for Solar Energy Research and Applications (TR)

The CST4ALL project is committed to catalysing an array of hybridisation and cooperation initiatives at the interface between CST and other renewable energy technologies targeting the electricity, heat, and fuels sectors.

To stay up-to-date on CST4ALL's activities and opportunities, follow-us on:

- LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/cst4all/>
- X (formerly Twitter): <https://twitter.com/Cst4All>
- Website: <https://cst4all.eu/en/>

You can also sign-up for the **CST4ALL Newsletter** to receive updates on other project events and outputs through the following link: <https://cst4all.eu/en/4169-contact-connect>.

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